

CURRENT STATE OF TEACHING THE SPECIALIZED PEDAGOGICAL MODULE AND FEATURES OF DEVELOPING STUDENT MOTIVATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15396647>

Abstract: This article analyzes modern approaches to teaching special pedagogy, methods of increasing students' internal motivation to learn, and innovative methods used to increase the effectiveness of the educational process. The article presents effective tools such as brainstorming, problem situations, interactive lessons, and information and communication technologies.

Keywords: special pedagogy, educational process, motivation, student activity, innovative methods, teaching technologies, individual approach

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются современные подходы к преподаванию специальной педагогики, методы повышения внутренней мотивации учащихся к обучению и инновационные методы, используемые для повышения эффективности образовательного процесса. В статье представлены эффективные инструменты, такие как мозговой штурм, проблемные ситуации, интерактивные уроки и информационно-коммуникационные технологии.

Ключевые слова: специальная педагогика, образовательный процесс, мотивация, деятельность учащихся, инновационные методы, технологии обучения, индивидуальный подход

Special pedagogy retains its relevance as an important science that provides for vulnerable population groups, ensures their social adaptation, and carries out professional orientation. Along with the requirements of modern society, the teaching of the special pedagogical module is also rising to a new level: the issues of an individual approach to the individual, an inclusive education system, the widespread introduction of information and communication technologies, and the development of student motivation deserve special attention today. Student activity in the educational process depends on their internal motivation in learning activities, which is directly

related to the teacher's deep understanding of methodological classroom work, lesson organization methods, and student psychology. Therefore, the development of student motivation in teaching the special pedagogical module is one of the main factors determining the level of professional training of future specialists.

Today, the reforms being carried out in the field of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, including the application of the principles of the Bologna Process, the competency-oriented model of education, as well as measures to improve the quality of education in higher educational institutions, further complicate the tasks of special pedagogy. At the same time, awakening students' interest in the subject, developing their ability to think independently, forming personal and professional qualities - all this serves to increase the effectiveness of the educational process. This requires the teacher to apply new approaches, innovative methods, and didactic tools in teaching this module.

The current state of teaching the special pedagogical module is implemented at different levels in different higher educational institutions. Although traditional lectures still prevail in many universities, as modern educational theories require, such methods as interactive lessons, practical classes, brainstorming, working on problem situations, role-playing, and preparing presentations are also widely used. These methods, along with attracting students' attention, encouraging their active participation, providing an opportunity to exchange ideas, also form such qualities inherent in specialists as leadership, empathy, decisiveness, and creative thinking.

The development of student motivation is carried out through the following main directions:

Personality-Marxist Approach: Each student's personal characteristics, areas of interest, intellectual potential, and learning objectives are taken into account. Through this, measures such as giving individual assignments, using a personal rating system, and personal mentoring practice are applied.

Application of innovative teaching methods: Information and communication technologies (ICT) - electronic educational platforms, online tests, video tutorials, virtual practice; interactive methods - group work, project-based learning activities, problem-based lessons, "Critical Thinking" are effective tools for increasing student motivation.

Professional orientation and connection with practice: Professional motivation is strengthened by linking the educational process of students to

practice, sending them for internships at various social service enterprises, and observing open lessons of specialists.

Award system: Incentivizing actively participating students, recognizing students who have achieved outstanding results, and creating opportunities to participate in competitions, scientific conferences, and olympiads are also of great importance in increasing motivation levels.

It should be noted that the most important condition for the development of motivation is the level of professional culture of the teacher, his understanding of student psychology, the ability to empathize, as well as the ability to make the learning process lifelike, logical, and interesting. As an individual, the teacher must also be an example for the student, inspire confidence in them, and strive to reveal their talents.

Thus, the current period of teaching the special pedagogical module can be analyzed as a developing process in accordance with modern educational standards. The development of student motivation in teaching this module is important not only for improving the quality of knowledge, but also for determining the level of professional training of future specialists. Motivation is not only a means of increasing educational activity, but also an indicator reflecting the dynamics of the general development of the individual. For this reason, special pedagogy teachers are tasked with awakening students' inner motivation, activating them, and forming their professional interests. For this, it is necessary to apply innovative teaching methods, use ICT, implement an individual approach, as well as closely link the educational process with practice.

Improving the teaching of the special pedagogical module in higher educational institutions is an urgent task directly related to the health of future generations of specialists, their sense of social responsibility, the culture of cooperation, as well as their professional qualifications.

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